

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2

ISSUE 21 APRIL-JUNE ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

ABRAHAM J. NAWANG

Assistant Professor I

Sulu State University

nawangabraham@gmail.com

“THE LAST PAGE OF MY LIFE”

I have reached the last page of the book. It is white, with black letters printed across it. I sit in a four-legged chair, facing a table where a lamp stands, casting light over the page. I read each word slowly, my eyes moving from line to line. I blink now and then when my eyes feel dry.

I breathe through my nose and out through my mouth; my chest rises and falls with each breath. My hands rest lightly on the table, my right fingers loosely holding a pencil. When I place both hands on the book, the paper feels smooth beneath my skin.

I look back at the words written before me, every line is already there. I do not write anything new, nor do I cross out what has been said. I read the first sentence again, then the second, then the third. They tell the story of what happened, what I did, and what I saw. I keep reading until I reach the final line.

It ends with a period, just a small dot. Beyond it lies only empty space, and there are no more pages after this one. I turn my head left, then right, and listen to the wall clock. It ticks steadily, each beat marking one second. I count them as I sit quietly.

When I finish, I close the book, bringing the front and back covers together. I rest my palm gently on top, pressing in flat against the table. The room is still, and the lamp continues to glow. I push my chair back, stand up, and feel my feet touch the floor. The book remains where it is; the story has come to an end.

I look my hands. Lines run across my palms, and my skin feels soft and warm. I bend my fingers at the joints, then reach out to touch the book's edge, sharp and straight. A thin layer of dust rest on the table beside it; I brush it away, and it settles softly on the floor.

I stand tall, hearing a faint creak from my knees. I take two steps back. The floor is wooden, and my shoes make a soft, quiet sounds against it. I stop and turn toward the window. Sunlight streams through the glass, and outside I see trees and wide, bright sky.

I walk back to the table and lift the closed book with both hands. It feels heavy, full of everything it holds. I carry it to a shelf along the wall, where many other books stand in a row. I place this one carefully between two others, aligning its spine neatly. I let go and step back; now it rests safely among the rest.

I sit down again, and the chair gives a soft groan. My back rest against the cushion, my feet flat on the floor. I fold my hands in my lap, my fingers still. My eyes stay fixed on the shelf where the book sits. The room is silent, no voices to be heard only the steady ticking of the clock.

I close my eyes for just three seconds before opening them again. The lamp is still lit, the book remains on the shelf, and the table stands in its place. The last page is no longer open, and the pencil lies unused. I do not reach for it, nor do I open the book once more. I stay seated, knowing the last page has been read, and the book is finally closed.

